

GEOTECHNICS

ТЕХНОЛОГІЇ ІНТЕЛЕКТУАЛЬНОГО ГЕОПРОСТОРОВОГО МОДЕЛЮВАННЯ ОЦІНКИ РИЗИКІВ БЕЗПЕКИ ТЕРИТОРІАЛЬНИХ ГРОМАД: НАПРЯМИ ЇХ РОЗРОБКИ

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TECHNOLOGIES FOR INTELLIGENT GEOSPATIAL MODELLING OF SECURITY RISK ASSESSMENT FOR TERRITORIAL COMMUNITIES: DIRECTIONS FOR THEIR DEVELOPMENT

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Анотація

Актуальність теми дослідження полягає у тому, сучасні особливості безпеки територіальних громад України в умовах ведення бойових дій мають глибоко комплексний характер, охоплюючи оборонні, економічні, екологічні, соціальні, інформаційні та правові аспекти. Поглиблення внутрішніх і зовнішніх негативних змін у сфері функціонування територіальних громад, наслідки ведення агресивних бойових дій потребують переосмислення підходів до протидії ризикам безпеки. Тому тема дослідження відносно розробки технології інтелектуального геопросторового моделювання оцінки ризиків безпеки територіальних громад має важливого значення.

Abstract

The relevance of the research topic lies in the fact that the current security issues of Ukraine's territorial communities in the context of hostilities are highly complex, covering defence, economic, environmental, social, informational and legal aspects. The deepening of internal and external negative changes in the functioning of

territorial communities and the consequences of aggressive hostilities require a rethinking of approaches to countering security risks. Therefore, the topic of research on the development of intelligent geospatial modelling technology for assessing the security risks of territorial communities is of great importance.

Ключові слова: інтелектуальне геопросторове моделювання, технологія, оцінка, ризику безпеки, територіальні громади, штучний інтелект, геоінформаційні системи.

Keywords: intelligent geospatial modelling, technology, assessment, security risks, local communities, artificial intelligence, geographic information systems.

Introduction. The current security issues facing Ukraine's territorial communities in the context of hostilities are highly complex, encompassing defence, economic, environmental, social, informational and legal aspects. The regulatory and legal framework is based on Resolution No. 1364 of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine dated 6 December 2022, which establishes the procedure for forming a list of territories where hostilities are or have been conducted or which are temporarily occupied, approved by the signatures of the Ministry of Reintegration and the Ministry of Defence on the basis of proposals from regional or city military administrations. This list provides for the planning of measures, but remains declarative, without providing tools for spatial assessment of community vulnerability.

Analytical data indicates that approximately 84% of Ukraine's territorial communities fall into the category of small communities, with a population of up to 30,000 people, which significantly limits their ability to implement modern security technologies. In these communities, ensuring sustainability has become a strategic priority. According to a 2024 survey, 8 out of 12 communities surveyed identified sustainability as their main task in the third year of the war.

Existing risk assessment methods remain fragmented and localised, focusing on specific sectors (environment, infrastructure, economy) or based on traditional statistical analysis, where spatial links and interdependencies are overlooked [1].

The automated collection of spatial data via satellite remote sensing systems, sensor networks, state registers and open data is insufficient, which complicates the formation of an operational, well-founded risk assessment. International scientific experience offers some approaches. In particular, the ICCROM project has already implemented a GIS-Based Risk Map for Ukraine's cultural heritage, which uses a combination of satellite imagery, local surveys and risk modelling [2].

In the field of geospatial monitoring, scientists have developed an open-source tool based on Sentinel-1 and machine learning that automatically assesses the probability of building damage across a territory [3].

The Linked Data approach is also used to unify information about geo-annotated events (with infrastructure damage), creating unified tools to improve the resilience of cities [4].

In the context of war, Ukraine also uses video data obtained with UAVs, which are used by artificial intelligence systems to recognise objects, assess the effectiveness of weapons, and train combat tactics [5].

The analysis of the regulatory framework confirms that the current state of the problem is determined by characteristics such as: the existence of regulatory, but overly general, regulation; the predominance of

small communities (~84%) with low capacity; fragmented risk assessment practices; lack of comprehensive automated spatial data collection; scientific and technological need to integrate GIS, artificial intelligence and risk modelling into a single adaptive platform.

In addition, existing trends in the development of scientific approaches indicate certain priorities aimed at ensuring the security of territorial communities in conditions of aggressive warfare. These include the need to create a theoretical and methodological platform and elements of security risk assessment technology to realise the potential of modern scientific and technical achievements; the development of a system of indicators and criteria for the classification and quantitative assessment of security risks, etc.

Literature Review. To develop and implement geospatial modelling technology for assessing the security risks of territorial communities in the context of armed aggression by the Russian Federation, methodological approaches have been proposed that combine classical methods of spatial analysis, artificial intelligence tools and mathematical modelling. Existing scientific developments lack unified approaches to defining a multi-level system for assessing the security risks of territorial communities and integrating spatial, environmental, social, and infrastructural factors into a single platform. Some scientists focus on the structural components of geoinformation analysis and cartographic risk modelling [6, 7]. Of particular importance is the approach to applying machine learning and fuzzy logic methods to account for uncertainty in forecast estimates [7].

Considerable attention is paid to the integration of artificial intelligence algorithms into the processes of satellite data analysis and geospatial information flows [8].

In terms of regulations, there is Resolution № 1364 of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine dated 6 December 2022 «On Approval of the Procedure for Forming a List of Territories Where Combat Operations Are (Were) Conducted or Temporarily Occupied», as well as the Law of Ukraine «On the Basic Principles of Civil Protection» (2004, as amended in 2023), which define the basic approaches of state policy in the field of territorial security and civil protection. Regulatory framework creates the conditions for the development of technology, but does not contain integrated mechanisms for spatial analysis and the implementation of innovative methods.

Purpose and objectives of the study. The aim of the study is to develop directions for geospatial modelling of TG security risk assessment in conditions of aggressive combat operations.

Main part. The methodological platform involves the use of multi-criteria analysis, in particular

the analytic hierarchy process (AHP) [9], integral risk indices and mathematical modelling of threat development scenarios. Deep learning algorithms (Convolutional Neural Networks, Recurrent Neural Networks) are expected to be used to process large amounts of geospatial data, to classify territories and predict impact scenarios [10]. The use of fuzzy set theory will ensure that the uncertainty inherent in crisis situations is taken into account [7]. Application of a methodological approach to categorical-theoretical modelling of information systems for the implementation of interaction between weakly structured processes and phenomena that influence the assessment of risks in territorial communities [11].

In practical terms, modelling is carried out using the QGIS software platform and Python libraries (TensorFlow, PyTorch, scikit-learn), which allow neural network algorithms to be integrated into cartographic processes. Spatial tasks of determining location, identifying changes and conditions will be formed through geostatistical tools – interpolation methods, hot spot analysis, clustering.

Taking into account international experience, primarily the UN recommendations within the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction (2015–2030) [12], the project will develop a system of indicators for the integrated assessment of community safety risks. Unlike existing approaches, the authors propose to implement a systematic approach that takes into account a combination of spatial, security, social and information factors, integrating classical tools of geoinformation analysis with innovative methods of artificial intelligence.

Data collection in accordance with international standards ISO 19115 (metadata for geospatial data) and INSPIRE Directive is of particular importance for the development of intelligent geospatial modelling technology for assessing the security risks of territorial communities, as it will ensure their compatibility and high quality. Compliance with FAIR principles is ensured by the following measures:

Findable. Each dataset will be published in open indexed repositories with a unique identifier (DOI), full description and metadata in accordance with ISO 19115. This will ensure that data can be easily searched by both humans and automated systems.

Accessible. Access to data and metadata will be provided through widely used and secure Internet protocols (HTTPS, OAI-PMH). Users will be provided with authorised access to restricted parts of the data (e.g., containing limited information for security reasons), but the metadata will remain accessible even if the datasets themselves are technically unavailable.

Interoperable. To ensure data compatibility with international scientific and management systems, data is presented in GeoJSON, GML, and NetCDF formats that support spatial attributes and analytical indicators. Metadata will contain cross-references to other open datasets and related studies.

Reusable. To ensure the reusability of data, all datasets are accompanied by detailed metadata (description of collection methods, model parameters, spatial layer characteristics).

The impact of the development and implementation of intelligent geospatial modelling technology for assessing the security risks of territorial communities on their economic and technological status has been determined, which is characterised by the completeness and reliability of the information obtained from the assessment of TG risks to improve the efficiency of planning and use of resources in the field of security. The technological impact is characterised by the introduction of a complex of geospatial analysis and AI for assessing the security risks of territorial communities, which optimises investments in those areas that most effectively meet security needs. It should be noted that there has been a reduction in the costs of managing emergency situations and a decrease in economic losses from crisis situations.

The implementation of intelligent geospatial modelling technology for assessing the security risks of territorial communities provides an opportunity to achieve social effects, including improving the security and quality of life of the population of territorial communities, ensuring the prediction of and timely response to emergencies and minimising their consequences, creating conditions and means for effective response to security risks by local self-government bodies and state structures, as well as involving the public in the processes of planning and managing territories and improving security.

The proposed technology creates a basis for improving the level of national security and defence capability of Ukraine in various fields. First and foremost, this is achieved by obtaining reliable spatial information through the formation of integrated geodatabases on TG security risks, the creation of a multi-level monitoring system that takes into account spatial, environmental, social, economic and defence factors, mapping mined territories, areas of destruction, critical infrastructure and potential threat zones, etc., and building geoinformation models for territorial defence and civil protection management. It should be noted that AI is used to increase the quality and quantity of spatial data collection and analysis for risk assessment. The developed theoretical and methodological platform and, based on it, the technology will allow the development of risk assessment indicators for the rapid response of the State Emergency Service, local administrations and military commands, and create the basis for managing evacuation processes, resource allocation and emergency response.

Conclusions. As a result of the research, a theoretical and methodological platform was developed, and based on it, elements of geospatial modelling technology for assessing the security risks of Ukraine's TG were developed. Their innovative nature is justified by the combined use of GIS, AI methods and mathematical modelling to solve complex security risk assessment tasks. This made it possible to form a comprehensive theoretical basis and practical tools aimed at creating an effective system for assessing risks and ensuring the security of TG.

A method of spatial modelling of integration risks combining GIS analysis and AI was proposed, which allows the collection, processing and analysis of spatial data for a comprehensive assessment of TG risks. A

risk classifier and a system of indicators with quantitative and qualitative assessment criteria adapted to the conditions of martial law have been developed, which provides an understanding of the challenges for ensuring TG security in the current circumstances.

A multi-level risk assessment model has been developed that combines spatial analysis, first-order logic and elements of category theory to reflect the interdependence of security factors, covering the tasks they affect, the most effective tools and means of implementing TG protection, revealing directions for predicting and most effectively overcoming the consequences of emergencies. This innovative modelling approach for assessing the risks of territorial communities is characteristic when used in combination with neural networks and artificial intelligence.

The methodological basis for assessing TG security risks has been improved, with factors taken into account in the classification, combining classical principles of spatial analysis and cartographic risk modelling, fuzzy set theory and fuzzy logic methods for working with the uncertainty of forecast estimates, categorical-theoretical modelling of information systems, concepts of geospatial analysis and artificial intelligence in the field of security, taking into account international standards and recommendations for risk assessment, in particular the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction (2015–2030) for the formation of a unified methodological approach to TG security risk assessment technology.

The algorithm for integrating data from various sources (satellite images, UAVs, sensor networks, state registers, open data) has been improved with the use of AI for automated or semi-automated data collection and analysis to obtain up-to-date information on the security status of TG.

Specific proposals have been formulated for local self-government bodies and state structures on the use of research results in planning security measures and community recovery strategies.

A concept of geospatial modelling for assessing TG security risks has been developed and implemented as a prototype in the form of a TG risk assessment model for Slobozhanshchyna, where hostilities took place.

A theoretical and methodological platform has been built and, on its basis, elements of technology for assessing the security risks of territorial communities using GIS and mathematical modelling based on AI, allowing scientific hypotheses to be formed and tested based on a clearly developed classification of security risks, justify new scientific approaches to the analysis and forecasting of TG risks using geographic information systems, integrate mathematical modelling and AI methods for processing spatial data characteristic of security risk assessment, and create a scientific basis for

the further development of methods, techniques and technologies for ensuring security.

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